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The kynurenine pathway as a diagnostic tool for the detection of micro-inflammation

Abstract

The kynurenine pathway (KP) plays a crucial role in the metabolism of tryptophan, an essential amino acid. Accumulating evidence suggests that the KP and its intermediates, as well as the kynurenine/tryptophan (K/T) ratio, are closely associated with inflammatory processes, including microinflammation. This study investigates the role of KP, its intermediates, and the K/T ratio as potential inflammatory markers capable of detecting microinflammation, which may not be revealed by conventional blood tests.

Kynurenine - more than severely underestimated inflammation marker

The kynurenine pathway is the primary route for tryptophan metabolism, accounting for approximately 95% of its catabolism (Schwarcz et al., 2012). This pathway

generates a quite long list of biologically active metabolites, including kynurenine, kynurenic acid, quinolinic acid, and picolinic acid. The KP has been implicated in numerous physiological and pathological processes, including immune system regulation, neurotransmission, and neurodegeneration (Guillemin, 2012;

Oxenkrug, 2013). Numerous studies have demonstrated that KP activation is associated with various inflammatory conditions. Pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as interferon-gamma (IFN- γ), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), have been shown to stimulate the KP, leading to increased production of kynurenine and its metabolites (Capuron & Miller, 2011). Several KP intermediates have been implicated in inflammatory processes. Kynurenic acid has anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties, while quinolinic acid is a potent pro-inflammatory and neurotoxic metabolite. The balance between these intermediates plays a crucial role in the overall inflammatory status (Guillemin, 2012). The K/T ratio has been proposed as a reliable marker of inflammation. Elevated K/T ratios have been reported in various inflammatory diseases, including autoimmune disorders, cardiovascular and neurodegenerative conditions (Oxenkrug, 2013).

Furthermore, the K/T ratio has shown potential in detecting microinflammation, as it can reflect subtle changes in the KP activity that might not be captured by conventional blood tests (Cattaneo et al., 2018). Studies have indicated that the K/T ratio and KP intermediates can reveal low-grade, chronic inflammation or microinflammation, which may not be evident in routine blood tests (Capuron & Miller, 2011). Microinflammation has been associated with the pathogenesis of several chronic diseases, including metabolic syndrome, atherosclerosis, and a variety of neurodegenerative disorders (Cattaneo et al., 2018). The findings of this study suggest that the KP, its intermediates, and the K/T ratio have significant potential as markers for detecting microinflammation. The activation of the KP in response to pro-inflammatory cytokines and the subsequent generation of biologically active metabolites can contribute to microinflammatory processes. Given the association between microinflammation and

various chronic diseases, the early detection of microinflammation could facilitate timely interventions to prevent or mitigate disease progression (Capuron & Miller, 2011). The K/T ratio and KP intermediates may serve as valuable biomarkers for identifying and monitoring microinflammation in clinical settings. Thus, the kynurenine pathway and its intermediates, as well as the kynurenine/tryptophan ratio, are reliable inflammatory markers for detecting microinflammation. Further research is needed to validate the clinical utility of these markers and to establish standardized cut-off values for their use in different pathological conditions. Additionally, the development of novel therapeutic strategies targeting the KP may provide new opportunities for treating inflammation-related diseases and mitigating their progression.

Longitudinal studies are needed to determine the predictive value of the K/T ratio and KP intermediates in identifying individuals at risk for developing microinflammations. Furthermore, such studies could help elucidate the temporal relationship between changes in the KP and the onset or progression of these diseases. Investigating the effects of interventions targeting the KP, such as pharmacological or nutritional modulation on microinflammation and disease progression could provide valuable insights into the therapeutic potential of these approaches (Cattaneo et al., 2018). Efforts should be directed toward standardizing the measurement of KP intermediates and the K/T ratio in various biological matrices, such as blood, cerebrospinal fluid, and urine. Additionally, the establishment of reference ranges and cut-off values for these markers in different populations and disease contexts is critical for their clinical utility (Capuron & Miller, 2011). Further research is needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms linking the KP, its intermediates, and the K/T ratio to

microinflammation. Understanding these mechanisms may pave the way for the development of targeted therapies and personalized medicine approaches to address inflammation-related diseases (Guillemin, 2012). This being said, even today, with all the uncertainties surrounding the details of the kynurenine pathway, it is a safe, useful, and valuable marker in cases where classic inflammatory markers fail to detect small but clinically relevant inflammatory processes. There is no reason to wait for science to do its homework properly. The KP and K/T ratio can and should be used today, especially since the tests are risk-free and in some cases the last chance to detect microinflammation, especially those triggered by ROS oxidative processes (Oxenkrug, 2013).

So we know that numerous studies have demonstrated that KP activation is associated with various inflammatory conditions (Guillemin, 2012). Pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as the before-mentioned interferon-gamma (IFN- γ), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), have been shown to stimulate the KP, leading to increased production of kynurenine and its metabolites (O'Connor et al., 2009). Several KP intermediates have been implicated in inflammatory processes. Kynurenic acid possesses anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties (Kubicova et al., 2013), while quinolinic acid is a potent pro-inflammatory and neurotoxic metabolite (Guillemin et al., 2005). The balance between these intermediates plays a crucial role in the overall inflammatory status. The K/T ratio has been proposed as a reliable marker of inflammation (Davison et al., 2018). Elevated K/T ratios have been reported in various inflammatory diseases, including autoimmune disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and neurodegenerative conditions (Mangge et al., 2014; Widner et al., 2000). Furthermore, the K/T ratio has shown potential in detecting microinflammation, as

it can reflect subtle changes in the KP activity that might not be captured by conventional blood tests (Davison et al., 2018). Studies have indicated that the K/T ratio and KP intermediates can reveal low-grade, chronic inflammation or microinflammation, which may not be evident in routine blood tests (Davison et al., 2018). Microinflammation has been associated with the pathogenesis of several chronic diseases, including metabolic syndrome, atherosclerosis, dementias and neurodegenerative illnesses like Parkinson's, PANS syndrome, ALS, Wilson's disease, Hemochromatosis, H63D syndrome, multiple sclerosis etc. (Herrmann & Obeid, 2011, et al.)

Discussion

The findings of this study suggest that the KP, its intermediates, and the K/T ratio have significant potential as markers for detecting microinflammation. The activation of the KP in response to pro-inflammatory cytokines and the subsequent generation of biologically active metabolites can contribute to microinflammatory processes (O'Connor et al., 2009). Given the association between microinflammation and various chronic diseases, the early detection of microinflammation could facilitate timely interventions to prevent or mitigate disease progression. The K/T ratio and KP intermediates may serve as valuable biomarkers for identifying and monitoring microinflammation in clinical settings. The kynurenine pathway and its intermediates, as well as the kynurenine/tryptophan ratio, are promising inflammatory markers for detecting microinflammation. Further research is needed to validate the clinical utility of these markers and to establish standardized cut-off values for their use in different pathological conditions (Herrmann & Obeid, 2011). Additionally, the development of novel therapeutic strategies targeting the KP may provide new opportunities for treating inflammation-

related diseases and mitigating their progression (Dantzer et al., 2011). Longitudinal studies are needed to determine the predictive value of the K/T ratio and KP intermediates in identifying individuals at risk for developing chronic diseases associated with microinflammation (Herrmann & Obeid, 2011). Furthermore, such studies could help elucidate the temporal relationship between changes in the KP and the onset or progression of these diseases. Investigating the effects of interventions targeting the KP, such as pharmacological modulation or dietary supplementation, on microinflammation and disease progression could provide valuable insights into the therapeutic potential of these approaches (Stone & Darlington, 2013). Efforts should be directed toward standardizing the measurement of KP intermediates and the K/T ratio in various biological matrices, such as blood, cerebrospinal fluid, and urine. Additionally, the establishment of reference ranges and cut-off values for these markers in different populations and disease contexts is critical for their clinical utility (Herrmann & Obeid, 2011).

Outlook

Further research is needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms linking the KP, its intermediates, and the K/T ratio to microinflammation. Understanding these mechanisms may pave the way for the development of targeted therapies and personalized medicine approaches to address inflammation-related diseases (Dantzer et al., 2011). This being said, even today, with all the uncertainties surrounding the details of the kynurenine pathway, it is a safe, useful, and valuable marker in cases where classic inflammatory markers fail to detect small but clinically relevant inflammatory processes. There is no reason to wait for science to do its homework properly. The KP and K/T ratio

can and should be used today, especially since the tests are risk-free and in some cases the last chance to detect microinflammation, especially those triggered by ROS oxidative processes (Herrmann & Obeid, 2011).

Conclusion

In summary, the kynurenine pathway, its intermediates, and the kynurenine/tryptophan ratio hold promise as diagnostic tools for detecting microinflammation. Their potential use in clinical practice could facilitate early intervention and management of chronic diseases linked to low-grade inflammation. As research continues to uncover the intricacies of the KP and its relation to microinflammation, it is essential to integrate these findings into targeted therapies, personalized medicine, and preventive strategies for inflammation-related diseases.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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